

Review Article

Therapeutic Drug Monitoring of Antimicrobials: A Key Component of Successful Patient Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: TDM is measurement of drug concentration in biological fluid to optimize patient's drug therapy. Therapeutic drug monitoring of antibiotics is very crucial as nowadays development of resistance towards antibiotics due to irrational use is indeed dangerous. **Methods:** A detailed online search was performed using Google Scholar to access peer reviewed abstracts, full journal articles and books applicable to the subject matter. Online search was done using terms such as TDM, antimicrobials, antibiotics, etc. The bibliographies of these articles were sources of additional articles. **Results:** To maximize efficacy and to minimize toxicity it requires an understanding of the pharmacokinetics (PK) of the prescribed antimicrobial and the susceptibility of the causative bacterial pathogen. Therapeutic drug monitoring act as an accurate method for dose adjustment for specific antimicrobials in concerned patient populations. **What is new and conclusions:** Therapeutic drug monitoring act as an accurate method for dose adjustment for specific antimicrobials in concerned patient populations. All hospitals do not have access to such facilities, and indeed suitable population PK models may not be available. Although the decreasing susceptibility of bacteria to available antimicrobials, as well as emerging data on pharmacokinetic variability, suggest that benefits are probable.

INTRODUCTION

The technique for determining drug concentrations in patients and utilizing those findings to create accustomed dosing regimens is known as therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) (dose, formulation, route, and frequency of administration) [1]. Maximizing the effectiveness whilst minimizing the toxicity of antimicrobial

agents is a crucial step in the treatment of infections. Adequate control of the source of infection is also important. However, knowledge of the pharmacokinetics (PK) of the prescription antibiotic and the susceptibility of the causing bacterial infectious agent is necessary to maximize efficacy and decrease toxicity. [2]. When it comes to the usage of particular patient populations' high

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morbidity and mortality rates [3-5], as well as intensifying resistance to antimicrobials [6] and increased cost of pharmaceuticals, Antimicrobial use optimization strategies should be taken into account. The aim of this manuscript is to review the place of therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) in the utilization of antimicrobial agents and discuss the issues regarding analysis of these drug concentrations.

Clinical experience must be of the highest calibre, especially when using medications with a limited therapeutic index. New opportunities are now accessible owing to recent technological advancements for fresh practical applications and enhanced clinical interpretation of single drug concentration measurements [7]. A significant amount of research has developed over the past 30 years to educate scientists and medical professionals on the concentration-effect relationships for antibiotics [8,9]. The following are some qualities of a drug for which therapeutic drug monitoring may be helpful and recommended: [10, 11].

- i) Drug has low therapeutic index and narrow therapeutic window, where dose producing positive clinical impact is close to dose likely to create negative effect.
- ii) There is no predictable dosage-response relationship, hence a dose that has positive effects in one person but negative effects in another is possible.
- iii) Because of the variability of plasma levels, drug concentration in the blood cannot be predicted by dose alone.
- iv) A drug's efficacy and toxicity both correlate with serum concentration, and unbound or free drug concentrations correlate with both better than total drug concentration.
- v) Dose adjustment cannot be predicated on any clearly defined clinical indicator, and it is complicated to track a drug's positive or negative effects.

vi) The likelihood of severe toxicity increasing the risk of fatal or irreversible organ damage.

Patients at the extremes of age, patients with dosage issues, patients taking numerous drugs, and patients with atypical PK as a result of physiological, environmental, illness, or genetic variables are significant specific populations where TDM is effective. [12]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A detailed online search was performed using Google Scholar to access peer reviewed abstracts, full journal articles and books applicable to the subject matter. Online search was done using terms such as TDM, antimicrobials, antibiotics, etc. The bibliographies of these articles were sources of additional articles.

To be appropriate for TDM, a drug must ideally fulfill the following factors:

Drug elements (must have all of these): large between subject variability; narrow therapeutic index; a demonstrated concentration-effect (or toxicity) relationship (or both);

Patient elements (any of these): suspected drug interactions; suspected drug adverse effects/toxicity; suspected drug abuse; unexplained failure of therapy; and suspected noncompliance. [12]

Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamic dimensions of antimicrobials

Pharmacokinetics examines the link between the dose administered and the concentration seen in body fluids and tissues. On opposite, Pharmacodynamics is the study of the connection between a drug's concentration and its result, or, in the case of an antibiotic, its capacity to eradicate or stop bacterial development. [13]

The impact of PK in therapeutic drug monitoring

Many antimicrobials will have "predictable" PK for patient populations, meaning that an antimicrobial dose suggested by the product information will consistently reach the desired

concentration limit. However, disease in some patients, such as the critically ill, may cause physiological alterations that have altered PK behavior. This topic has already been discussed in depth elsewhere [14, 15]. It is sufficient to state that altered drug clearances [16–19], as well as variable volumes of distributions [20], are prevalent in various patient populations, making the prognosis of medication exposure challenging.

Inter individual differences in PK and PD are particularly important in "special populations," those who are more probable to either under- or over-respond to typical dosing regimens, who are least capable of tolerate, recognize, or communicate drug effects, who have organ dysfunction, or who are deliberately or unintentionally dosed incorrectly. [21]

The role of MIC in therapeutic drug monitoring

One crucial component of the PK/PD of antibiotics is the MIC. In each of the PK/PD instances, the MIC serves as the denominator and, as such, indicates the PK exposure required to produce the desired PK/PD ratio. The significance of increasing PK exposure in relation to the pathogen's MIC is demonstrated by the fact that MICs are given in multiplication factors of two, meaning that each degree of decreased susceptibility requires an increase in PK exposure. (e.g. MIC increase from 1 to 2mg l–1 it is necessary to double the PK component in to maintain the ideal PK/PD ratio. For instance, a targeted Cmax/MIC ratio of 8-10 is advised when prescribing gentamicin. [8]

Antimicrobial classes preferred for TDM

Mechanism of action of aminoglycosides

Fig. 1 Mechanism of action of aminoglycosides

Nowadays, evaluating the therapeutic benefits of aminoglycosides is a common clinical method (such as tobramycin, gentamicin, and amikacin). Although avoiding toxicities was the initial purpose, dose plans and TDM objectives are increasingly being developed to maximise efficacy. [23] It will be more complicated for a given dose of a concentration-dependent antibiotic to reach the target Cmax with an enlarged volume of distribution. TDM can be used to determine whether a greater dose accomplishes the intended goal by doing a sample 30 minutes after the intravenous infusion has ended. [24] Many sick people have compromised renal function. If the dose is retained, decreased aminoglycoside clearance will raise the risk of toxicities. (e.g. nephrotoxicity or ototoxicity). It is advisable to increase the dosing frequency in certain circumstances. Elevated aminoglycoside and renal clearances may be observed in other people, such as burns patients, which may indicate the need for an additively lower dose frequency. [2, 20]

How to monitor aminoglycoside antimicrobials: Only in cases where the patient's volume of distribution is markedly different from "typical" patients would monitoring of Cmax be necessary. Hence, it might reasonable to monitor Cmax in individuals who are critically ill, obese, or have burns. It has been recommended that concentrations be assessed anywhere between 6

hours after dosage and trough concentrations to confirm that adequate clearance is occurring. Some individuals may not benefit from trough concentration monitoring for once-daily dosing because their concentrations might not be detectable. In situations of renal failure, trough concentration monitoring is advised for dosing every 36 or 48 hours to ensure that redosing does not put toxicities at risk. To assist in dosing, several nomograms, such as Sawchuk and Zaske [25], MacGowan and Reeves [26], Begg [27] and Nicolau [28] nomograms. The relative benefits of these approaches has been discussed by Begg and Barclay. [29]

However, the effects of aminoglycoside TDM are most apparent when health outcomes are improved. The therapeutic importance of aminoglycoside TDM was studied using a comparative multicenter examination of 232 hospitalised patients, comparing a "conventional" TDM technique to a "active" TDM strategy. [30] There is very little, if any, debate in the scientific literature regarding the protocols that support TDM of the aminoglycosides. Aminoglycoside immunoassay procedures used today are still quite promising. [31]

Glycopeptides

There are two antimicrobials in the glycopeptide class: teicoplanin and vancomycin. Vancomycin is typically administered, and TDM is often carried out. Moise-Broder et al. [32] An AUC₀₋₂₄/MIC ratio of 400 was thought to be associated with improved clinical results and faster bacterial eradication in a retrospective analysis of inpatients that examined the link between AUC₀₋₂₄/MIC and outcomes in patients with methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* pneumonia. Professional societies support this goal as well. [33, 34]

Jeffres et al. [35] have demonstrated a substantial correlation between trough concentrations and AUC₀₋₂₄, elevating them to the level of a useful metric and approach for monitoring vancomycin

dosage despite the fact that AUC₀₋₂₄ is not frequently observed in clinical settings. [33, 36]

Additionally, it has been suggested that in order to accomplish concentration targets more effectively, loading dosages up to 35 mg (per kg bodyweight) may be used. [34, 37]

Despite the lack of a clearly documented mechanism and epidemiology for VAN, it remains to be a potentially dangerous side effect that demands urgent attention as vancomycin use rises in response to an increasing number of illnesses driven on by resistant gram-positive bacteria [25].

β -Lactams

Mechanism of action of β -Lactams

Fig.2 Mechanism of action of β -Lactams

The therapeutic window for these antibiotics is wide, hence β -Lactam TDM has not been thoroughly studied. The objectives for β -lactam TDM remain unanswered. [53] The free (or unbound) antibacterial concentration should be kept above the MIC ($fT > MIC$) according to in vitro and in vivo (animal) evidence. The PD target is suggested to be between 40 -70% for the time. [38, 39] In contrast, data from recent retrospective analyses support the maintenance of a prolonged $fT > MIC$ in critically ill patients. [40-43]

Reverse phase chromatography (RPC) utilising C18 columns is used in around 90% of assays for β -lactams, which are primarily measured by HPLC. [44] Samanidou et al.'s analysis of more than

80 reports found that 76% of the assays used ultraviolet detection.^[44] The most accurate assay for quick assessment of multiple β -lactams can measure 12 drugs simultaneously with a 7 min runtime by simultaneously monitoring three distinct wavelengths.^[45] This kind of test is precise enough to be used in a planned TDM programme.^[46]

Linezolid

Despite variable pharmacokinetics in patient populations and indicated robust pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic objectives, there is less information available to explain the possible function for TDM of linezolid ^[49, 50, 51]. There is no proof that TDM reduces the frequency of toxicities such as bone marrow suppression, peripheral neuropathy, and lactic acidosis despite the fact that these have been associated with linezolid treatment^[51]. This issue is highlighted in the study by Zoller and colleagues ^[52], who examined the levels of LZD in 30 critically ill patients. The study's findings corroborate new research suggesting that therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM), which has historically been used to reduce harmful effects, should also be utilised to optimise dose in critically sick patients. LZD dosage and administration procedures need to be optimised. Although more research on each of the aforementioned methodologies is required before concrete recommendations can be made, it seems reasonable to use TDM where it is available ^[53].

Other antimicrobials

A few other antimicrobials have been added to TDM, although many of them have unstable PKs and might be candidates.

Quinolones

The PK/PD indices for the various quinolones against many bacteria have been accurately described ^[54], so dose adjustment to meet these targets may become more common given the issues with subtherapeutic dosing and the

emergence of resistance. There are few papers available that discuss quinolone TDM.^[55]

Antituberculoïd

Mechanism of action of Rifampin

Fig.3 Mechanism of action Rifampin

Some data on these medications' evidentiary pharmacokinetic variability support the use of TDM. In one investigation, isoniazid and rifampicin measured concentrations were found to be out of the therapeutic range in 77 and 48% of patients, respectively^[56]. Numerous anti-TB medications exhibit significant inter-individual variation. Contrary to failure, relapse, or toxicity for the patient, TDM can also resolve complex drug-drug interactions. TDM is a very valuable ally in the handling of difficult clinical illnesses in many respects^[57].

CONCLUSION

In populations of concerned sufferers, therapeutic drug monitoring serves as an accurate tool for dose adjustment for specific antibiotic. When possible, Bayes' theorem should be applied to dosage modification, however not all hospitals will have access to these resources, and relevant population PK models may not be accessible. Although increasing information on pharmacokinetic variability and the decreasing susceptibility of bacteria to current antibiotics show that advantages are likely. TDM is valuable in a variety of therapeutic circumstances, such as those involving patients who would be more likely to

encounter treatment failure, those who respond slowly, etc. The possibility of satisfactory clinical and bacteriological results is increased by using TDM to attain the desired serum concentrations.

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